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Salt Tolerance Mechanisms and Strategies for Enhancing Crop Productivity in Vegetable Crops: A Review

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Abstract

Salinity limits crop production, affecting over 1.4 billion hectares (10.7% of global land area) of the world's land. Factors like low rainfall, high evaporation, poor water management, and excessive fertilizer use contribute to soil salt accumulation. Salt tolerance, a complex trait influenced by multiple genes, reduces growth rates, alters leaf characteristics, and disrupts nutrient balance. However, salinity also has positive effects on quality and disease resistance. Understanding salt tolerance mechanisms is important for developing mitigation strategies. Genetic variations exist within and among species, with allopolyploid species and crops/varieties adapted to saline soils showing higher tolerance. Strategies for enhancing salt tolerance include developing halophytes, utilizing interspecific hybridization, using existing variation, and generating variation through selection, mutagenesis, or tissue culture. Grafting, selection, interspecific hybridization, tissue culture, and genetic engineering are approaches to developing salt-tolerant crops. Techniques like marker-assisted breeding and genetic transformation hold promise. Specific strategies for improving salt tolerance in selected vegetable crops (brinjal, carrot, pea, pepper, potato, okra, onion, tomato) involve treatments with methyl jasmonate, polyamines, inorganic nutrients, potassium, humic acid, inorganic fertilizers, plant growth regulators, grafting, and genetic approaches. Understanding the genetic, biochemical, and physiological mechanisms underlying salt tolerance is important for enhancing productivity under salinity.

Keywords: Salinity; Salt tolerance; Halophytes; Vegetable; Saline soils

Introduction

Salinity is an abiotic stress that limits crop production, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions where precipitation can be insufficient for leaching (Muhammad et al., 2024). More than 1.4 billion ha of land or over 10% of the world's land is affected by salinity (Singla-Rastogi, 2025). Various environmental factors, including low rainfall, high evaporation, poor water management, and excessive use of chemical fertilizers, cause the accumulation of salts in the soil (Tarolli et al., 2024). Soil is considered saline when it has sufficient salt in the root zone to impede crop growth, and the USDA Salinity Laboratory defines saline soil as having an electrical conductivity (EC) of the saturation extract of 4 dS m⁻¹ or more (Shahid, 2012).

Crop salt tolerance is ultimately determined by the yield performance of farmers, but evaluating yield under saline conditions is extremely challenging due to the variability of salinity within yields (Atta et al., 2023) and the potential interactions with other environmental factors (e.g., gaseous pollutants, soil fertility, drainage, temperature, light flux density, and transpirational water loss) (Gavrilescu, 2021). Thus, yield performance is commonly assessed in trial plots or using a solution-based method with readily adjustable salinity, although the latter does not permit yield

measurements due to lack of space, and estimates of tolerance obtained from such experiments do not always correspond to the plant's response in the field (Flowers, 2004). The evaluation of crop salt tolerance is further complicated by the variation in sensitivity to salt during the life cycle, as grain yield in rice is much more affected by salt than its vegetative growth, and germination is relatively salt-resistant (Afzal et al., 2023). In tomato, tolerance during germination was not linked to the ability to grow under salt stress, as these processes were regulated by distinct mechanisms. However, some genotypes exhibited similar tolerance levels at both germination and vegetative growth stages (Singh et al., 2024).

Salinity Effects

Salinity generally reduces growth rate, resulting in smaller leaves and sometimes fewer leaves, due to osmotic effects (Tian et al., 2020). Root length and mass are also reduced, while the maturity rate is either delayed or accelerated depending on the species. Salinity response severity is mediated by environmental interactions (Atta et al., 2023; Lahlali et al., 2025) and depending on the saline solution composition, ion toxicities or nutritional deficiencies arise (Alharbi et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022). Osmotic effects of salinity contribute to reduced growth rate, changes in leaf colour, root/shoot ratio, and maturity rate. Ionic effects are visible in leaf and meristem damage or as symptoms typical of nutritional disorders. High concentrations of Na^+ or Cl^- result in the 'scorching' or 'firing' of leaves, while nutritional deficiency symptoms are generally similar to those that occur in the absence of salinity. Calcium deficiency symptoms are common when Na/Ca ratio is high in soil water (Kumar et al., 2021).

However, salinity also has favourable effects on yield, quality, and disease resistance. Spinach yields initially increase at low to moderate salinity (El-Nakhel et al., 2022; Ors et al., 2016). Sugar contents increase in carrots, and starch content decreases in potatoes as salinity rises (Bernstein, 1959; Sola et al., 2025). Cabbage heads are more solid at low salinity levels but less compact as salinity increases (Deepa Devi and Arumugam, 2019). Celery has been reported to be both more resistant and more susceptible to blackheart under saline conditions (Banyal et al., 2019; Deepa Devi and Arumugam, 2019; Shannon et al., 1999).

Mechanism of salinity tolerance

Salinity tolerance in plants is a complex trait that involves multiple adaptive mechanisms at morphological, physiological, biochemical, and molecular levels (Arif et al., 2020) (Fig.1). To survive under salt stress, plants regulate water balance by minimizing water loss and improving root water uptake (Acosta-Motos et al., 2017; Singh N et al., 2024). They also produce compatible solutes like proline and glycine betaine to maintain cellular stability and metabolic functions (Abobatta, 2020). Additionally, ion compartmentalization within vacuoles helps prevent toxicity, ensuring proper cellular function (Hao et al., 2021). On a molecular scale, plants activate defence responses such as the synthesis of stress proteins, antioxidant enzymes, and other protective molecules to counteract oxidative stress (Kesawat et al., 2023). Based on their tolerance levels, plants are classified as glycophytes, which are sensitive to high salinity, or halophytes, which can thrive in saline environments (Pandey and Gayen, 2024). Improving salt tolerance in glycophytes is a key area of research, with strategies such as genetic modifications, transcription factor regulation, and grafting techniques being explored. Given the challenges posed by soil salinization, enhancing crop resilience is essential for sustainable agriculture (Zuzunaga-Rosas et al., 2023).

Three Distinct Types of Plant Response or Tolerance

The mechanisms of salinity tolerance fall into three categories:

Tolerance to osmotic stress: Osmotic stress promptly limits cell expansion in root tips and young leaves while also triggering stomatal closure. A weaker response to osmotic stress enables greater leaf growth and stomatal conductance; however, the increased leaf area is advantageous only when adequate soil water is available (Zhao et al., 2020).

Na^+ exclusion from leaf blades: The exclusion of Na^+ by roots prevents sodium from accumulating to harmful levels in leaves. If this exclusion mechanism fails, toxicity develops over days or weeks, depending on the species, leading to the early death of older leaves (Yousaf et al., 2022).

Tissue tolerance: Tolerance to accumulated Na^+ or, in some species, Cl^- involves the ability to compartmentalize these ions at both cellular and intracellular levels. This prevents toxic concentrations from building up in the cytoplasm, particularly in the mesophyll cells of leaves. Over

time, toxicity develops when Na^+ levels become excessively high in older leaves (Rahman et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2020).

Fig. 1. Salinity tolerance mechanism in vegetable crop plants.

Table 1. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance, organized by plant processes and their relevance to the three components of salinity tolerance (Alzubaidy 2020; Shah et al., 2021; Tester 2008; Wei et al., 2023).

Process Involved	Candidate Genes	Osmotic Stress Response	Ionic Stress Response (Na^+ Exclusion)	Ionic Stress Response (Tissue Tolerance)
Membrane Transport and Ion Homeostasis	<i>CNGCs, V-ATPase, AKT1, CHX, NHXs</i>	Maintenance of cell turgor by regulating ion channels	Selective ion transport to maintain Na^+/K^+ balance	Optimized cellular compartmentalization of toxic ions
Antioxidant Defense Mechanisms	<i>APX, SOD, CAT, GPX, GST</i>	Protection against oxidative stress due to dehydration	Minimization of ROS generation linked to Na^+ toxicity	Strengthened ROS scavenging capacity in stressed tissues
Perception and Signaling in Roots	<i>SOS3, SnRKs, CIPKs, CDPKs</i>	Regulation of long-distance signaling for stress response	Modulation of ion flux towards the shoot	Enhancement of vacuolar ion compartmentalization
Na^+ Partitioning in Shoots	<i>HKT, SOS1, NAX1, NRT1</i>	Increased osmotic adaptation	Restriction of Na^+ translocation to aerial parts	Reduction of metabolic energy demand for Na^+ exclusion
Synthesis of Compatible Solutes	<i>P5CS, OTS, MT1D, M6PR, S6PDH, IMT1</i>	Accumulation of organic solutes for osmotic stability	Adjustment of solute transport to limit Na^+ buildup	Enhanced production of osmoprotectants in cytoplasm
Photosynthetic Efficiency	<i>ERA1, PP2C, AAPK, PKS3, ABI1</i>	Reduced stomatal closure to conserve water	Prevention of ionic toxicity in chloroplasts	Delayed onset of chloroplast ion toxicity
Sequestration of Na^+ in Vacuoles	<i>NHX, AVP, TIP, TPK</i>	Improved water retention through osmotic regulation	Enhanced storage of Na^+ in root vacuoles	Increased Na^+ accumulation in vacuoles of leaf cells
Shoot Growth Regulation	<i>ARFs, AUX/IAA, GA200x, DELLA</i>	Promotion of cell expansion and lateral bud development	Not directly involved	Delay of premature senescence to sustain carbon supply

Genetics of salinity resistance

Genetic variation for salinity resistance exists among and within species. Estimating the range of this variability, especially within species, is important for breeding programmes for salinity resistance. Evaluating the yield of genetically different materials under a range of salinity levels is the most reliable approach (Atieno et al., 2017; Kapazoglou et al., 2023).

Interspecific and intraspecific variations have shown that allopolyploid species and crops/varieties adapted to saline soils are generally more tolerant of saline soils (Ashraf and McNeilly, 2004). Lyon, (1941) was among the earliest researchers to study the genetic basis of salt tolerance. An interspecific cross between *Lycopersicon esculentum* and *L. pimpinellifolium* revealed that the hybrid's fruit yield was more affected by increasing sodium sulfate levels than either of its parent plants. Other crosses of wild and cultivated tomatoes also suggested complex genetics (Moreels et al., 2023). Analysis of other species has also suggested that the genetics of salt tolerance is complex. Evidence of dominance of tolerance is also seen with pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan*) (Singh et al., 2023) and sorghum crop (Jeon et al., 2023; Peduzzi et al., 2024), showing heterosis, dominance, and additive effects. While assessing tolerance is complicated by changes occurring during the growth of a plant and to be technically difficult under field conditions, there is evidence of a genetically complex trait (Kumari and Mesfin, 2015; Flowers, 2004). Information on inheritance of salinity resistance is limited due to the complex nature of salinity resistance and the difficulties in creating precisely controlled and dependable salinity environments.

Approaches to enhancing tolerance

Flowers and Yeo (1995) outlined five methods for improving salt tolerance in crops, which were considered effective at the time. The first approach involved cultivating halophytes as alternative crops. Since halophytes naturally thrive in saline environments, they could serve as viable options for agricultural production in salt-affected areas. The second method suggested using interspecific hybridization to enhance salt tolerance in existing crops. By crossing salt-sensitive crops with their more tolerant wild relatives, it would be possible to introduce beneficial traits that improve resilience to salinity. Another strategy focused on utilizing the natural genetic variation already present in crop species. Some varieties naturally exhibit higher salt tolerance, making them valuable resources for breeding programs aimed at improving overall resistance. The fourth approach involved creating new variations within crops through techniques such as recurrent selection, mutagenesis, or tissue culture. These methods could increase genetic diversity and provide opportunities for developing cultivars with improved salt tolerance. Finally, rather than focusing solely on tolerance, they recommended selecting plants based on their yield performance under saline conditions. This approach ensures that productivity remains high while still maintaining some level of salt resistance. In view of the importance of salinity, considerable efforts have been invested in breeding for salinity-resistant varieties. The various approaches for the development of salinity-resistant cultivars are as follows:

Salinity resistance root stocks

Grafting tomato plants for increased salinity tolerance is a promising practice to improve crop performance in saline soil. Singh et al. (2020) and Santa-Cruz et al. (2001) found an increase in growth and fruit yield when a salt-sensitive tomato cultivar was grafted onto a tolerant rootstock and irrigated with water containing 50mM NaCl. Alqardaei et al., (2024) also reported that grafting improves salt tolerance, determined as fruit yield, in a commercial tomato hybrid grafted onto several tomato rootstocks with different potentials to exclude saline ions and grown at different NaCl concentrations. Bayoumi et al. (2021) and Zhu et al. (2008) concluded that the reduction in root dry weight of grafted cucumber plants was significantly lower than that recorded in ungrafted plants under NaCl stress. Moreover, grafted cucumber plants tended to accumulate more biomass in root resulting in a greater root-to-shoot ratio in comparison to ungrafted plants (Abbas et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2009). Finally, using squash and bottle gourd rootstocks under saline stress conditions, the reduction in root dry weight was significantly lower in grafted than ungrafted watermelon plants. Therefore, the better growth performance of grafted vegetable crops exposed to salinity stress might be attributed to differential root growth under salinity stress.

Selection

Selection has been effective in developing salinity resistance lines with improved stress performance. The cultivated tomato species has been hybridized with salt-tolerant wild species to improve its tolerance. Mutations in *Lactuca serriola*, followed by natural and artificial selection, likely facilitated the emergence of primitive lettuce forms exhibiting increased biomass and enhanced salinity tolerance. These genetic and phenotypic adaptations have been instrumental in

the domestication and subsequent diversification of cultivated lettuce (Xu and Mou, 2015). A salt-tolerant line was developed through backcrossing *L. cheesmanii* to the cultivated parent (Fredrickson and Epstein, 1975; Rush and Epstein, 1976, 1981a; Solis et al., 2020). *L. pennellii* was hybridized and backcrossed to New Yorker for nine generations, and breeding lines from this cross had higher salt tolerance than the cultivated parent (Sacher et al., 1982; Torgeman et al., 2024). A processing tomato variety with improved salt tolerance was selected in Israel from an interspecific backcross with *L. pennellii*. Four cycles of recurrent selection have produced a line with high salt tolerance and superior quality characteristics (Guo et al., 2022; Shannon and Noble, 1990). Screening 85 lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) varieties showed high variability in salt tolerance (Shannon et al., 1983; Xu and Mou 2015). Salinity primarily affected shoot growth in lettuce at low salinities, but growth and head-to-frame ratio in crisp head lettuce can be improved through selection (Adhikari et al., 2019; Shannon, 1980). 115 lettuce introductions showed higher salt tolerance and variability for the characters than cultivated varieties and breeding lines (Hassan et al., 2021; Shannon and McCreight, 1984). In field trials, Romaine varieties were more salt tolerant than iceberg varieties (Kappel et al., 2021; Schrader, 2017).

Interspecific Hybridisation

Evidence of dominance for salt tolerance was also seen with pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*), where a cross with *Atylosia albicans* produced intergeneric hybrids that behaved as the wild parent, indicating dry weight production was determined by a dominant genetic factor (Flowers, 2004; Saxena et al., 2023). An F₁ muskmelon hybrid has been produced from selected parents of salt-tolerant and locally adapted melon varieties in Israel (Chauhan et al., 2021; Dogimont and Sari 2022; Shannon and Noble, 1990). The selected hybrid, BG84-3, had improved productivity and salt tolerance in preliminary yield trials. In Egypt, a muskmelon variety, Shad El-Dokki, has been selected for superior yields under saline conditions (Shannon 1997; Sharma and Goyal 2003).

Tissue culture

The use of undifferentiated cells in tissue culture to improve salt tolerance has been explored in various crops (Buyukdinç et al., 2022; Rajan et al., 2021). Tissue cultures provide large populations of cells that can be maintained under controlled environmental conditions and manipulated easily. Tissue cultures are suitable for mutagenesis, haploid production, somatic hybridization, and transformation. However, the regeneration process in tissue cultures can result in the loss of the selected trait, which is a significant limitation (Bijalwan, 2021; Wijerathna-Yapa and Hiti-Bandaralage, 2023).

Genetic Engineering

Evidence suggests that salt tolerance and its sub-traits are influenced by multiple gene loci (Naem et al., 2020). In an intergeneric cross of tomato, quantitative trait loci (QTL) were found associated with fruit yield in plants growing under saline conditions, although some QTL were dependent on the parentage of the cross (Diouf et al., 2018). QTL are treatment-sensitive (Khan et al., 2016), with some associated with aspects of fruit yield found regardless of whether the plants were grown with or without salt, and others detected only under saline or non-saline conditions (Rosca et al., 2023). Other crosses have identified both stress-specific and stress-nonspecific QTL, with the latter generally exhibiting larger individual effects and accounting for a greater portion of the total phenotypic variation under each condition (Foolad et al., 1999; Rabbi et al., 2022). Mutagenesis has identified plant genes required for osmotic stress tolerance in tomato, with a novel mutant in tomato (*tos1*) found to be hypersensitive to general osmotic stress (Borsani et al. 2002; Salava et al., 2021). The *tos1* mutant is less sensitive to intracellular abscisic acid (ABA), which is a basic cellular trait expressed by the mutant at all developmental stages analysed, and is not caused by a deficiency in ABA synthesis because the *tos1* seedlings accumulated more ABA than the wild type after osmotic stress. In contrast, the *tss2* tomato mutant is hypersensitive to exogenous ABA. Comparative analysis of *tos1* and *tss2* indicates that appropriate ABA perception and signalling are essential for osmotic tolerance (Andrade et al., 2008; Seo and Marion-Poll, 2019).

Bohnert and Jensen (1996) suggested that Flowers and Yeo had overlooked an important approach in plant tolerance breeding, stating that the successful release of tolerant crops would require "metabolic engineering" involving the transfer of many genes. While this approach was not feasible in the 1990s (Flowers and Yeo, 1996), it is now being widely advocated. In experiments reported between 1993 and 2003, some species, including rice, tobacco, and Arabidopsis, have been transformed with nearly 40 genes. Transformations involving the synthesis of compatible solutes have been the most popular, with those involving glycine betaine being the most commonly performed (Table 2 and 3).

Table 2. Genes used in the transformation of plants which claimed enhancement of salt tolerance

Activity	Genes
Apoplastic invertase	<i>Apo-Inv</i>
Arginine decarboxylase	<i>ADC</i>
Betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase, BADH, betB, choline dehydrogenase (CDH) choline oxidase, codA (glycinebetaine)	<i>betB, codA</i>
Ca ²⁺ -dependent protein kinase	<i>CDPK</i>
Ca/H antiporter	<i>CAX1</i>
Calcium-binding protein	<i>EhCaBP</i>
Calicneurin; protein kinase	<i>CaN</i>
Ca protein kinase	<i>OsCDPK7</i>
Glutathione S-transferase and glutathione peroxidase	<i>GST and GPX</i>
Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, GPD	<i>GPD</i>
Glycogen-synthase kinase-3	<i>AtGSK1</i>
Glutamine synthetase	<i>GS2</i>
Heat shock protein	<i>DnaK/HSP70</i>
High-affinity potassium transporter	<i>HKT1a</i>
Isopentenyl transferase (increased cytokinin)	<i>ipt</i>
Late embryo abundant protein (a LEA)	<i>HVA1</i>
Mannitol 1-phosphate dehydrogenase	<i>mt1D</i>
Myo-inositol O-methyltransferase (ononitol)	<i>IMT1</i>
Omega-3 fatty acid desaturase (fatty acid processing)	<i>fad7</i>
Proline transporter	<i>AhProT1</i>
Proton sodium exchanger	<i>HNX1a</i>
Putative transcription factor	<i>Alfin1</i>
Rare Cold Inducible gene 3	<i>RCI3</i>
Rice <i>Hal2</i> like, <i>RHL</i>	<i>Hal2</i>
S-adenosylmethionine decarboxylase, (spermine, spermidine)	<i>SAMDC</i>
Serine/threonine kinase	<i>AT-DBF2</i>
Sorbitol-6-phosphate dehydrogenase	<i>SPD</i>
SR-like, putative splicing protein	<i>SR</i>
Transcription factors	<i>DREB1A and AhDREB1</i>
Trehalose-6-phosphate synthase/phosphatase (trehalose)	<i>TPSP</i>
Yeast halotolerance gene	<i>Hal2</i>
Yeast halotolerance gene	<i>Hal1</i>
Yeast mitochondrial superoxide dismutase	<i>Mn-SOD</i>
Vacuolar H ⁺ -pyrophosphatase	<i>A VP1</i>

Table 3. Species used in the transformation of plants which claimed enhancement of salt tolerance

Sr. No.	Plant species	References
1	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	Li et al. (2024)
2	<i>Brassica napus</i> and <i>B. juncea</i>	Mondal and Chakraborty (2020); Qian et al. (2024)
3	Citrus (<i>Carrizo citrange</i>)	Vives-Peris et al. (2023)
4	<i>Cucumis melo</i> (melon)	Behera et al. (2022); De Abreu Araújo et al. (2025)
5	<i>Diospyros kaki</i> (Japanese persimmon)	Gil-Munoz et al. (2020)
6	<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i> (tomato)	Guo et al. (2022); Xu et al. (2015)
7	<i>Medicago sativa</i> (alfalfa)	Lin et al. (2024)
8	<i>Nicotiana tabaccum</i> (tobacco)	Azameti et al. (2024); Huma et al. (2015)
9	<i>Solanum melongena</i> (eggplant)	Behera et al. (2022); Wang et al. (2025)
10	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i> (potato)	Lin et al. (2025); Zeid et al. (2022)

Improvement of mineral nutrient uptake

Reactive O₂ species (ROS) are increasingly recognized as a significant cause of cell damage in crop plants under salt stress (Li et al., 2025). Low concentrations of NaCl have been found to stimulate the activities of antioxidant enzymes in several plant species, indicating a role of salt stress in the formation of ROS (Alvan et al., 2025). Studies using inhibitors and O₂ production have shown that a plasma membrane-bound NADPH oxidase is involved in the generation of O₂ following salt treatments (Kabała et al., 2022). In line with this, overexpression of superoxide dismutase (SOD) in chloroplasts of rice plants has been shown to prevent salt stress-induced cell damage (Bogoutdinova et al., 2020).

Similarly, In tobacco cell cultures, salt-induced O₂ generation by NADPH oxidase was strongly inhibited by Zn, indicating that improving the Zn nutritional status of plants growing in saline conditions could protect against salt toxicity (Song et al., 2025). Zn has been found to maintain the structural integrity of the plasma membrane, controlling the uptake of Na and other toxic ions (Singh et al., 2024), but its protective role against ROS suggests that Zn ions also protect salt-stressed plants from damaging ROS attack (Mushtaq et al., 2020).

Some strategies to improve growth and yield of selected vegetable crops

CARROT (*Daucus carota* L.)

Carrot is a widely cultivated root vegetable known for its nutritional and medicinal properties, though its cultivation is significantly affected by salinity stress, which hampers germination, growth, and overall yield (Malcolm and Smith, 1971; Swamy, 2022). Research indicated that for every unit increase in electrical conductivity beyond the threshold of 1.0 dS m⁻¹, root yield declines by approximately 14% (Mohammed et al., 2023).

Salt-tolerant carrot varieties exhibit specific physiological and biochemical mechanisms to counteract osmotic and ionic stress. Kamińska et al., (2022) reported that these plants activate protective responses, primarily in the roots, to mitigate oxidative damage. The accumulation of osmoprotective compounds such as proline, glutathione, and ascorbic acid, along with enhanced antioxidant enzyme activity, plays a critical role in maintaining cellular stability. Additionally, the ascorbate–glutathione cycle contributes to reactive oxygen species (ROS) regulation under saline conditions. Salt-tolerant varieties also demonstrate more efficient ion compartmentalization, reducing sodium and chloride toxicity, thereby improving overall stress tolerance.

Effective irrigation strategies have also been investigated to manage soil salinity and optimize water use. Nagaz et al. (2012) demonstrated that irrigation scheduling based on soil water balance (SWB) was more effective in sustaining yield and controlling soil salinity compared to conventional farmer practices. Full irrigation (FI-100) resulted in the highest yields while preventing excessive salinity buildup in the root zone. Meanwhile, regulated deficit irrigation (FI-DI60) proved to be a viable alternative, maintaining comparable yields with reduced water consumption. However, greater deficit irrigation levels (DI-80 and DI-60) led to yield reductions, and the traditional farmer's method caused inefficient water use and increased soil salinity.

Water stress has been shown to have a more detrimental impact on carrot germination and seedling growth than salt stress. Studies indicate that soil moisture potentials of -0.01 MPa negatively influence these early stages, whereas osmotic potentials as low as -0.5 MPa do not cause significant reductions. Root development exhibits a positive response to matrix potentials between -0.1 and -0.3 MPa, demonstrating a differential response to matric and osmotic stress. Interestingly, under non-limiting water conditions, salinity levels up to 16 dS m⁻¹ do not alter the transpiration coefficient, suggesting that salinity has a limited impact on water-use efficiency in the absence of ion toxicity or nutrient imbalances (Schmidhalter and Oertli, 1991).

Several approaches have been explored to mitigate the negative effects of salinity on carrot growth. Matera et al., (2025) found that inoculation with the endophytic bacterium *Pantoea vagans* SRS89 significantly enhanced seed germination and seedling growth under saline conditions. At 150 mM NaCl, inoculated seeds exhibited increased germination rates by 30% and 18% for 1-hour and 3-hour treatments, respectively. Additionally, treated plants displayed improved morphological traits, higher chlorophyll b and carotenoid levels, and increased soluble sugar content, indicating enhanced stress resilience. These findings suggest that *P. vagans* SRS89 could be a promising bioinoculant for improving carrot tolerance to salinity in field conditions. Overall, carrot's sensitivity to salinity presents a significant challenge to its cultivation, necessitating careful management of soil salinity and water availability to maintain optimal growth and yield. The use of bioinoculants, optimized irrigation practices, and the development of salt-tolerant cultivars present promising strategies to support carrot cultivation in saline environments.

BRINJAL (*Solanum melongena* L.)

Brinjal (Eggplant) exhibits moderate sensitivity to salinity, with early growth stages being particularly vulnerable to salt stress (Hannachi and Van, 2018; Mady et al., 2023; Suarez et al., 2021). Jameel et al., (2024) demonstrated the significant effects of salinity on different brinjal (*Solanum melongena*) varieties, showing variations in their ability to tolerate salt stress. High salinity conditions negatively impacted plant growth, leading to reduced shoot and root length, lower chlorophyll content, and a decline in protein levels. However, the study also revealed adaptive

responses, such as an increase in antioxidant enzyme activity (peroxidase, catalase, and superoxide dismutase), as well as elevated flavonoid, anthocyanin, and lycopene levels. These biochemical adjustments suggest that brinjal plants activate protective mechanisms to counteract salt-induced oxidative stress. Among the four varieties examined, ICS-BR-1351 exhibited the highest level of salt tolerance, making it a strong candidate for cultivation in saline environments.

Exposure to high salinity levels leads to a reduction in germination rate, seedling biomass, and overall growth parameters, including radicle and hypocotyl development (Bhati et al., 2021). Under saline conditions, sodium (Na^+) accumulation in seedling leaves increases, while potassium (K^+) levels and the K^+/Na^+ ratio decline, negatively impacting ion homeostasis (Assaha et al., 2017). However, as the plant matures, its ability to tolerate salt stress improves (David et al., 2022). Salt stress also disrupts key physiological functions by reducing shoot and root biomass, limiting gas exchange processes such as CO_2 assimilation, transpiration, and stomatal conductance, while altering internal CO_2 concentration (Giordano et al., 2021). Interestingly, water use efficiency in eggplant remains stable under saline conditions, although overall water consumption declines (Damasceno et al., 2022; Khalid et al., 2023). Additionally, salinity lowers K^+ and calcium (Ca^{2+}) levels and the K^+/Na^+ ratio while increasing Na^+ and chloride (Cl^-) concentrations. In response, eggplant accumulates higher levels of glycinebetaine and proline, which function as osmoprotectants to mitigate stress effects (Abbas et al., 2010; Sanwal et al., 2022). The impact of salinity on yield is significant, as both fruit weight and the number of fruits per plant decrease under high salt conditions.

Ali et al. (2024) determined that brinjal (*Solanum melongena*) exhibited sensitivity to salinity, which adversely affected its growth, yield, and physiological processes. Salt stress caused a decline in biomass, photosynthetic pigments, and primary metabolites, while it led to an increase in antioxidant enzyme activities and secondary metabolite production. However, the application of citric acid (CA), particularly at concentrations of 200 and 300 ppm, significantly reduced the negative impacts of salinity. It improved plant growth, enhanced yield, increased photosynthetic pigment content, and strengthened antioxidant enzyme activities. Several strategies have been explored to improve eggplant resilience to salt stress. The application of inorganic fertilizers, compatible solutes, and beneficial microbes, along with grafting techniques, has been effective in enhancing tolerance (Elwan, 2010; Sanwal et al., 2022). Foliar application of di-potassium hydrogen orthophosphate (K_2HPO_4) has been shown to support plant growth, increase fruit yield, and improve total soluble sugar content under saline conditions, while also enhancing leaf K^+ and Ca^{2+} concentrations (Devi and Arumugam, 2019; Elwan, 2010; Imran et al., 2024). The external application of glycine-betaine (GB) has also demonstrated positive effects on eggplant development in saline environments.

Additionally, the use of plant growth-promoting bacteria, such as *Pseudomonas sp. DW1*, has been found to enhance salt tolerance by improving germination rates, increasing shoot Ca^{2+} content, and boosting antioxidant enzyme activity (Dutta et al., 2021; Fu et al., 2010). Grafting eggplant onto *Solanum torvum* rootstocks has proven to be an effective approach for increasing salt tolerance, as it promotes stronger growth and maintains better physiological and biochemical functions under saline conditions (Cerruti et al., 2021; Alkhatib et al., 2021; Jameel et al., 2024).

OKRA (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.)

Salinity stress has a detrimental effect on the growth and yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*), though the crop exhibits moderate tolerance compared to other vegetable species (Motamedi et al., 2021; Najafi et al., 2024). One of the primary effects of salinity is the inhibition of seed germination, which is associated with increased sodium (Na^+), sugar, and phenol content, along with a reduction in potassium (K^+), starch levels, and amylase enzyme activity (Xiong et al., 2024; Dkhil and Denden, 2010). Salinity-induced physiological stress disrupts metabolic activities and enzyme functions, leading to reduced crop productivity (Ali et al., 2021).

Habib et al. (2016) demonstrated that okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) was highly sensitive to salinity, particularly during its early growth stages. However, the application of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) with ACC deaminase significantly improved its tolerance. Among the tested strains, *Enterobacter sp. UPMR18* proved to be the most effective, enhancing seed germination, promoting shoot and root growth, increasing chlorophyll levels, and boosting antioxidant enzyme activities such as SOD, APX, and CAT under saline conditions. Additionally, the inoculated plants showed increased expression of ROS pathway genes, which helped reduce oxidative stress. These

results suggested that *Enterobacter sp. UPMR18* could be a valuable tool for improving okra resilience to salinity, providing a sustainable solution for cultivation in salt-affected soils.

Morphological and physiological traits of okra, including shoot and root biomass, total leaf area, shoot length, and fresh pod yield, are significantly impacted under saline conditions (Abd El-Fattah et al., 2020). However, some physiological parameters, such as transpiration rate, stomatal conductance, leaf water potential, and turgor pressure, remain relatively stable even under salt stress (Arif et al., 2020). Salinity also influences pigment composition, as chlorophyll a content and the chlorophyll a/b ratio increase, whereas chlorophyll b and carotenoid levels show little to no variation (Ashraf et al., 2003; Mendonca et al., 2023). Although the overall photosynthetic efficiency is considerably inhibited, the gas exchange characteristics are not significantly altered (Shahbaz et al., 2012).

Haq et al. (2023) highlighted significant genetic variability among different okra genotypes, influencing their ability to tolerate saline conditions. Some genotypes demonstrated high salt tolerance, maintaining better growth and yield despite salt stress, making them suitable candidates for breeding programs aimed at developing salt-tolerant okra varieties. Salinity was found to negatively affect plant height, pod yield, and physiological traits such as relative water content (RWC) and the potassium-to-sodium (K^+/Na^+) ratio, which are crucial for maintaining plant health under stress. They categorized okra genotypes into salt-tolerant and salt-susceptible groups, with the tolerant varieties exhibiting lower sodium (Na^+) accumulation and a higher K^+/Na^+ ratio, which play key roles in salinity adaptation. These findings underscore the importance of selecting and breeding salt-tolerant cultivars to ensure sustainable okra production in regions affected by salinity. To enhance salt tolerance in okra, various agronomic and biochemical strategies have been explored. The application of potassium (K) and organic compounds, such as humic acid, has been found to improve salt resistance, particularly during the seedling stage (Paksoy et al., 2010; Shehata et al., 2023). These findings highlighted the potential of nutrient management and organic amendments as effective approaches to mitigate salinity stress and sustain okra production under saline conditions.

ONION (*Allium cepa* L.)

Onion is highly sensitive to salinity, exhibiting minimal genetic variation in salt tolerance among cultivars. While germination is relatively tolerant, seedling growth is highly sensitive, with tolerance increasing at the three- to five-leaf stage. Salt stress causes leaf discoloration (dull blue-green) and tip burn symptoms (Regessa et al., 2022; Solouki et al., 2023).

Patel (2019) examined the effects of saline irrigation on five onion varieties (GJWO-3, GJRO-11, Talaja Red, Pilli Patti, and PWF-131) under four salinity levels (<2.0, 4.0, 6.0, and 8.0 $dS\ m^{-1}$). Salinity stress led to reductions in plant height, bulb size, and chlorophyll content, with onion plants showing varying tolerance across growth stages. Pilli Patti (V₄) demonstrated the best performance in growth and biochemical traits, including the lowest Na^+/K^+ ratio, highest proline accumulation (0.96 $\mu mol\ g^{-1}\ FW$), and improved ion regulation. Higher salinity reduced biomass and bulb weight but increased proline content, aiding stress tolerance. Bernstein and Ayers (1953) found that yield decline begins at an EC_e threshold of 1.4 $dS\ m^{-1}$, with a 50% reduction at 4.1 $dS\ m^{-1}$. Salinity reduces bulb size, weight, root growth, plant height, and leaf count while increasing bulb ion content and dry weight. Onions may mature a week earlier under saline condition.

Venancio et al. (2022) highlighted onion (*Allium cepa* L.) as a crop highly affected by salinity stress, which leads to decreased growth, yield, and overall physiological stability. Elevated salinity in irrigation water negatively influences bulb weight, total production, and water efficiency while also deteriorating post-harvest characteristics such as firmness and pH levels. Salinity stress triggers physiological disruptions, including reduced water retention and increased ion leakage. However, silicon (Si) fertilization plays a beneficial role in mitigating these effects by enhancing osmolyte accumulation, antioxidant activity, and ion balance. The application of Si has shown to improve onion yield and bulb quality under moderate salinity conditions (EC 1.7–2.8 $dS\ m^{-1}$). They suggest that incorporating Si fertilization into salinity management strategies can enhance onion cultivation in affected regions. Pasternak et al. (1984) suggested that early-stage sensitivity is due to the plant's small, shallow rooting system, though no studies have explored genetic modifications for improved tolerance. Wannamaker and Pike (1987) observed that onion germination remained unaffected up to 20 $dS\ m^{-1}$ but declined sharply beyond 30 $dS\ m^{-1}$, with no significant cultivar differences.

Bose et al. (2025) identified 24 GATA genes (*AcGATAs*) in onion (*Allium cepa* L.), examining their structure, expression patterns, and role in stress adaptation. They showed that most of these genes responded to salinity stress, with 22 exhibiting increased expression at various time points. The presence of stress-related regulatory elements in their promoter regions suggested their involvement in salt tolerance mechanisms.

PEA (*Pisum sativum* L.)

Pea is highly sensitive to salinity, exhibiting greater susceptibility compared to other legumes such as broad bean (*Vicia faba*), common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), and soybean (*Glycine max*) (Ben Gaied et al., 2024; Bouzroud et al., 2023; Khan and Basha, 2015; Yousef et al., 2020). Salinity stress significantly impairs pea growth, particularly affecting seed germination and early seedling development (Fareed et al., 2024). Ehtaiwwesh and Emsahel, (2020) demonstrated that salinity stress had a negative impact on the germination and growth of pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) plants. While the plants tolerated lower salinity levels (50mM NaCl), higher concentrations (100mM and 150mM NaCl) significantly reduced germination rates, seedling vigor, and overall growth. Increased salinity restricted water absorption, which led to poor seedling establishment and decreased biomass. The findings indicated that pea plants were highly sensitive to extreme salinity (150mM NaCl), resulting in severe reductions in plant height, branching, leaf development, and overall growth.

Rooting medium salinity has been linked to growth inhibition, with increased salt concentrations leading to further reductions in overall plant development (Ahmad and Jhon, 2005; Piwowarczyk et al., 2016). Studies indicate that while low salinity levels primarily restrict shoot growth, root development remains largely unaffected. However, under higher salinity conditions, both shoot and root growth experience substantial declines (Cordovilla et al., 1995; Borucki and Sujkowska, 2008; Khan et al., 2022). A direct correlation exists between increased salinity and reduced pea yield, with reports of a 50% reduction occurring at moderate salinity levels (100 mM NaCl) (Hamouda et al., 2023).

Unlike other crops, genetic engineering approaches to improve pea's salt tolerance remain unexplored, with conventional methods being the primary means of mitigating salt-induced stress. Pretreatment with methyl jasmonate (Me-JA) has demonstrated effectiveness in protecting key physiological functions, including CO₂ fixation, soluble protein content, Rubisco activity, and photosystem II efficiency (Farhangi-Abriz and Ghassemi-Golezani, 2019). Additionally, Me-JA treatment helps regulate Na⁺ and Cl⁻ accumulation in the shoot, likely through its roles in osmoregulation, osmoprotection, and ionic homeostasis (Sharma et al., 2019; Slama et al., 2015). Similarly, the exogenous application of polyamines at micromolar concentrations has been found to mitigate K⁺ efflux in pea mesophyll cells under salt stress, suggesting a role in stabilizing ion transport across plasma membranes (Pottosin et al., 2021; Shabala et al., 2007; Shahid et al., 2020). Nutrient supplementation has also been explored as a strategy to alleviate salinity stress in pea. The addition of boron (B) and calcium (Ca) has shown positive effects in improving germination and vegetative growth under moderate salinity conditions (El-Aidy et al., 2021; El-Hamdaoui et al., 2003). However, at higher salinity levels (≥150 mM NaCl), these treatments were less effective (Bonilla et al., 2004; Nusrat et al., 2014).

Furthermore, Ca and B supplementation contributed to the recovery of salt-damaged root nodules, enhancing nitrogen fixation efficiency (Bolanos et al., 2006). The negative effects of salt-induced potassium (K) and iron (Fe) deficiencies were also mitigated through B and Ca application (Azeem et al., 2021; El-Hamdaoui et al., 2003). Salinity stress has been linked to alterations in the pectin composition of pea cell walls, leading to structural damage; however, supplementation with Ca and B has been reported to restore cell wall integrity (Vera-Maldonado et al., 2024). However, the application of chitosan (CS), particularly at 50 mgL⁻¹, alleviated these negative impacts by enhancing plant growth, reducing electrolyte leakage and sodium ion accumulation, and boosting antioxidant activity. Additionally, CS-treated plants exhibited improved yield parameters even under high salt stress. Among the two pea varieties tested, Polo demonstrated greater resilience to salinity, indicating its suitability for cultivation in saline environments (Anjum et al., 2025).

PEPPER (*Capsicum annuum* L.)

Pepper exhibited moderate sensitivity to salinity, though susceptibility varies depending on the growth stage (Zamljen et al., 2022; Jameel et al., 2024). High salt concentrations negatively impact plant morphology, physiological processes, and overall yield (Butt et al., 2021). A reduction in shoot and root biomass under saline conditions is often linked to a decrease in total leaf area, net CO₂ assimilation, and stomatal conductance (Orosco-Alcala et al., 2021). In response to salinity-induced

oxidative stress, pepper plants generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can damage cellular components. However, the plant's defense mechanisms activate antioxidant responses to mitigate this stress (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2020).

Shams et al. (2024) investigated how salinity stress affects seed germination, 1000-seed weight, plant growth, and proline content in three pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) genotypes: Maras, Carliston, and Dolmalik: under greenhouse conditions. Plants were exposed to salinity levels of 0.7, 3.5, and 7 dS m⁻¹, showing varied responses. Maras exhibited the highest proline content, leaf area, and plant biomass, demonstrating greater salinity tolerance. Carliston and Dolmalik experienced significant reductions in seed germination (60% and 68%, respectively) under 7 dS m⁻¹, whereas Maras showed a milder 27% decrease. Similarly, 1000-seed weight declined by 20.73% in Maras, compared to 36.12% in Carliston and 34.39% in Dolmalik. Research by Lee, (2006) indicates that enzymatic antioxidants, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), ascorbate peroxidase (APX), and glutathione reductase (GR), play a crucial role in reducing oxidative damage in salt-affected plants.

Salinity also affects the water balance in pepper plants, leading to a decline in osmotic potential as external salt levels rise. Despite this, leaf turgor pressure is generally maintained, suggesting an adaptive mechanism to regulate water retention (Altuntas et al., 2024; Kumawat et al., 2023). The timing of salt exposure is a key factor in determining its impact. Seeds germinating in saline conditions experience more severe growth inhibition compared to plants that encounter salinity after establishment (Shams et al., 2024).

Hassan et al. (2025) highlighted various approaches to enhancing salinity tolerance in crops, including genetic, molecular, physiological, and agronomic strategies. Microbial applications involved introducing beneficial microorganisms into saline soils to promote plant growth and stress tolerance. In peppers, these microbes improved growth, boosted antioxidant defenses, and enhanced capsaicin content. Their effectiveness lay in increasing nutrient uptake, stimulating growth hormones, and reducing oxidative damage. Genetic modifications offered another pathway to salinity tolerance by enhancing the plant's ability to regulate ion transport. In some crops, genes that helped retain potassium while limiting sodium accumulation were identified and utilized. Similar genetic approaches could have been applied to develop salt-tolerant pepper varieties through selective breeding or biotechnology. Soil amendments such as biochar, silicon, and humic acid played a crucial role in mitigating salinity stress. These amendments improved soil structure, enhanced nutrient retention, and reduced toxic ion buildup. Silicon supplementation, in particular, showed promise in maintaining ion balance and supporting plant growth under saline conditions. Combining these approaches provided a more effective strategy for managing salinity stress in peppers.

Several techniques have been investigated to improve pepper's tolerance to salt stress. Seed priming with NaCl has been reported to enhance germination and seedling growth under saline conditions (Johnson and Puthur, 2021). The application of essential nutrients such as manganese (Mn), calcium (Ca), and zinc (Zn) helps mitigate oxidative damage by reducing ROS accumulation (El-Beltagi et al., 2024). Additionally, calcium supplementation in the root zone has been found to restore calcium homeostasis, which is often disrupted by salinity stress (Shahid et al., 2020; Usman et al., 2023). Pre-sowing seed treatments with compounds like glycine-betaine and ascorbic acid have shown positive effects in alleviating salinity stress, leading to improved seed germination and early plant development (Othaimen, 2015). These treatments also enhance mesophyll cell function, improving physiological responses under saline conditions (Aman Shamil, 2022).

POTATO (*Solanum tuberosum* L.)

Potato, moderately salt-tolerant but are more sensitive during tuber bud initiation, with increased salinity reducing tuber size (Chourasia et al., 2021). Raspor et al., 2024 found that potato plants with reduced cytokinin (CK) levels demonstrated greater resistance to mild salt stress (50–100 mM NaCl) but struggled under severe salinity conditions (150–200 mM NaCl). At lower salt concentrations, these plants showed less visible damage, stronger rooting, better water retention, and stable chlorophyll levels. However, at higher salt concentrations, their ability to activate antioxidant enzymes was compromised, leading to increased sensitivity and lower survival rates. Jaarsma and De Boer (2018) found that Desiree, a salt-tolerant potato cultivar, manages salinity stress better than Mozart due to its superior vacuolar Na⁺ transport. Desiree maintains vacuolar H⁺ pump activity more effectively, while Mozart experiences a greater decline under salt stress. Additionally, Desiree's Na⁺/H⁺ antiport system is more efficient in Na⁺ transport and retention. Unlike Mozart,

which shows reduced vacuolar H⁺ pump protein levels after salt exposure, Desiree retains stability in these proteins. As a result, Mozart accumulates more Na⁺ in its leaves, disrupting water balance and increasing osmotic stress. These traits contribute to Desiree's stronger salt tolerance.

Gowayed et al. (2017) demonstrates that silicon dioxide nanoparticles (SiO₂-NPs) significantly enhance the salinity tolerance of potato plants. Under salt stress, SiO₂-NPs (especially at 50 mg L⁻¹) improve growth by enhancing water uptake, regulating ion balance, and boosting defense mechanisms. Increased activity of antioxidant enzymes (GPX and SOD) suggests reduced oxidative stress, while protein analysis indicates activation of stress-related genes. However, a higher concentration (100 mg L⁻¹) proved toxic, reducing growth and enzyme activity. Thus, while SiO₂-NPs offer a promising strategy for improving potato crop resilience in saline conditions.

Massa et al. (2024) highlighted the effectiveness of in vitro selection in improving salt tolerance in three potato varieties: Svenja, Safari, and Taurus. Increased salt concentrations negatively impacted growth parameters, though Svenja exhibited greater resilience. Higher proline levels were observed under salt stress, suggesting its role in stress adaptation. Callus induction and regeneration success varied, with Svenja achieving the highest regeneration rates. Several regenerated lines (S₉, S₁₀ from Svenja; T₁, T₂ from Taurus; SF₁, SF₅ from Safari) demonstrated strong tolerance to high salt levels (200–250 mM NaCl). They confirmed the potential of callus culture as a valuable method for developing salt-resistant potato genotypes. Gypsum application has been beneficial for salt-stressed potatoes (Abdullah and Ahmad, 1982). A study at the U.S. Salinity Laboratory found a 50% yield reduction at 6.2 dS m⁻¹ (Bernstein, 1959). Salinity impacts plant emergence, growth, and maturity but does not significantly affect tuber quality (Levy, 1992; Nadler and Heuer, 1995). Some cultivars, such as Atica and Desiree, exhibit greater salt tolerance, while wild species like *S. kurzianum* show higher resilience by accumulating Na⁺ (Sabbah and Tal, 1995).

TOMATO (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.)

Tomato is moderately sensitive to salt stress, with its tolerance levels varying across different growth stages and among cultivars. Salinity stress significantly affects physiological functions, leading to reduced growth and yield. Studies indicate that a 50% yield reduction occurs at salinity levels between 5.0 dS m⁻¹ and 8.0 dS m⁻¹, depending on the genotype and environmental conditions (Thakur et al., 2022; Ali, 2020). The adverse effects of salinity on tomato plants include alterations in morphological attributes, reductions in shoot and root biomass, decreased plant height, and lower total leaf area (Ullah et al., 2020; Ikram et al., 2024). Although moderate salinity can enhance fruit quality, excessive salt levels compromise both vegetative and fruit growth, particularly in salt-sensitive cultivars (Sora et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2024).

The physiological efficiency of tomatoes is also negatively impacted by salinity, as evidenced by reductions in leaf water potential, osmotic potential, and stomatal conductance. An increase in endogenous abscisic acid (ABA) concentrations under saline conditions suggests a stress-induced regulatory mechanism to mitigate water loss (Song et al., 2023). Additionally, salinity leads to a decline in nitrate reductase activity due to reduced nitrate uptake and increased chloride accumulation, further exacerbating nutrient imbalances (Wang et al., 2024). Previous studies highlight that salt tolerance in tomato involves complex genetic regulation. Microarray analysis has identified numerous genes associated with salt stress, emphasizing that salt tolerance is governed by multiple genetic pathways (Ouyang et al., 2007).

To enhance salt tolerance, several strategies have been explored, including the application of inorganic fertilizers, plant growth regulators, and other chemical compounds (Begum et al., 2019; Sabagh et al., 2021). Supplementing the growing medium with potassium (K) and calcium (Ca) has been shown to improve growth under saline conditions (Garcia-Marti et al., 2019). Additionally, the exogenous application of amino acids and growth regulators like thidiazuron and salicylic acid enhances tomato growth and physiological function under salt stress (Shahbaz et al., 2012). Other pre-conditioning strategies, such as osmotic treatment of seedlings and pre-seed treatments, have also demonstrated potential in improving salt tolerance (Zhang et al., 2022).

Grafting onto salt-tolerant rootstocks has emerged as an effective method for mitigating salinity stress. Grafted plants exhibit improved ionic homeostasis, enhanced antioxidant enzyme activity, and higher photosynthetic efficiency under saline conditions (Singh et al., 2020; Albacete et al., 2009). The positive impact of grafting has been attributed to the rootstock's ability to regulate ion transport, preventing excessive sodium accumulation in the shoots. Similarly, genetic improvement

through marker-assisted breeding has been employed to identify and introduce salt-tolerant traits in commercial tomato cultivars (Paudel et al., 2020). Quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping has revealed multiple chromosomal regions associated with salt tolerance, suggesting that genetic regulation plays a crucial role in stress adaptation (Foolad et al., 1997).

Biotechnological approaches, including *CRISPR-Cas9* gene editing, offer promising solutions for developing salt-tolerant tomato lines. Recent research has identified key genes such as *HKT1* and *NHX1*, which regulate ion homeostasis and osmotic adjustment under saline conditions (Li et al., 2022). Transgenic approaches have demonstrated that overexpressing salt-tolerance genes, such as *AtNHX1* from *Arabidopsis thaliana*, significantly enhances tomato survival under high salinity (Singh et al., 2021). Additionally, functional genomic studies using mutants have identified key loci, such as *tss1*, that play essential roles in salinity tolerance (Alo Sora, 2019; Borsani et al., 2001).

Al-Gaadi et al., (2024) demonstrated that salinity levels exceeding 9.5 dS m⁻¹ significantly reduce leaf transpiration, stomatal conductance, photosynthesis, chlorophyll content, and overall yield. However, moderate salinity levels of up to 6.0 dS m⁻¹ did not cause substantial yield reductions, particularly in grafted plants, which exhibited improved photosynthetic efficiency. The accumulation of proline in grafted plants further contributed to osmotic regulation and stress adaptation. Consistent with Rouphael et al., (2018), this study confirms that salt-tolerant tomato varieties maintain higher potassium-to-sodium (K⁺/Na⁺) ratios and better osmotic balance, aiding in improved stress tolerance. Additionally, findings align with Thakur et al., (2022), who reported that salinity beyond 3.0 dS m⁻¹ significantly reduces plant height, fruit weight, and total yield, primarily due to ion toxicity and osmotic stress.

Overall, the integration of agronomic, physiological, and molecular strategies is essential for mitigating the effects of salinity stress on tomato production. Further research into molecular mechanisms and biotechnological interventions will be crucial in developing resilient tomato varieties capable of thriving under saline conditions.

Table 4. Improvement in salt tolerance of potential vegetables crops using different strategies

Vegetable crops	Strategy employed to improve salt tolerance	Trait improved	References
BEETROOT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of potassium silicate (K₂SiO₃) Foliar spray of ascorbic acid and gibberellic acid Microbial inoculation with mycorrhiza 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased root yield -Higher pigment content (betalains) -Improved salinity tolerance 	Abdel-Moneam et al. (2024); Yasmeein et al. (2019)
BROCCOLI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foliar application of urea or methyl-jasmonate (MeJA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improved growth 	Del Amor and Cuadra-Crespo, (2010); Rios et al. (2021)
CABBAGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silicon application in nutrient solution Exogenous application of chitosan Grafting onto salt-tolerant rootstocks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improved root morphology -Increased salt tolerance -Higher yield under salinity 	Hegazi and El-Shrai, (2017); Reddy et al. (2024)
CARROT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foliar application of selenium (Se) Silicon (Si) supplementation in growth medium Exogenous application of proline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enhanced root growth -Increased shoot biomass -Improved water use efficiency 	Duborska et al. (2022); El-Ramady et al. (2024); Qirat et al. (2018)
CAULIFLOWER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrogen application to growth medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased yield 	Samiksha et al., 2023
EGGPLANT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foliar application of dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate (K₂HPO₄) Exogenous application of glycinebetaine (GB) as foliar spray Inoculation with plant growth-promoting bacteria Grafting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased fruit yield -Increased growth and yield -Increased dry biomass -Increased shoot fresh biomass 	Ayub et al. (2020); Aman Shamil (2022); Ayub et al., (2022); Elwan, (2010); Gruda et al., (2024)

LETTUCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exogenous application of jasmonic acid (JA) Soil amendment with organic matter and compost Use of salt-tolerant rhizobacteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improved osmotic adjustment -Increased chlorophyll content -Higher fresh weight 	Ayuso-Calles et al. (2023); Neto et al. (2024); Ouhaddou et al. (2022)
OKRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of K and humic acid in saline medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased dry biomass 	Samiksha et al., (2023)
PEA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-sowing seed treatment with methyl jasmonate (Me-JA) Exogenous application of polyamines Inorganic nutrient like B and Ca application in nutrient medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased proline content -Increased seed yield - Increased nodule number and efficiency 	Aslam et al., (2021); Zaidi et al., (2024)
PEPPER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of Mn, Ca, Zn, and N sources and humic acid Exogenous application of glycinebetaine, ascorbic acid, and NaCl as pre-sowing seed treatment Foliar application of 24-epibrassinolide Transgenic approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improved salt tolerance with high K⁺ and Ca²⁺ uptake -Increased dry biomass - Increased shoot dry weight - Survived at high salinity levels 	Pinto-Marijuan et al., (2023); Zohaib et al., (2024)
POTATO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-treatment of potato tuber with NaCl and CaCl₂ salts Application of potassium to the rooting medium Exogenous application of plant growth regulator, 5-aminolevulinic acid Relative humidity Transformation of cultivar Desiree using Arabidopsis thaliana stress-induced promoter <i>rd29A</i> and the <i>DREB1A</i> gene Potato line expressing a bacterial catalase gene 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased shoot dry weight - Increased yield -Increased MDA and POD activities -High RH improved growth - Improved stress tolerance -Increased chlorophyll content and yield 	Chourasia et al., (2021); Mondal et al., (2022); Liu et al., (2023); Zhai et al., (2024)
SPINACH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of calcium nitrate (Ca(NO₃)₂) Exogenous application of salicylic acid Use of biochar in soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased leaf area and photosynthetic efficiency -Improved antioxidant activity -Reduced Na⁺ accumulation 	Eraslan et al. (2008); Sofy et al. (2022); Omar et al. (2020)
TOMATO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of K and Ca to saline medium Exogenous application of amino acids, thidiazuron, and salicylic acid Grafting Transgenic tomato overexpressing <i>AtNHX1</i> (gene controlling vacuolar Na⁺/H⁺ antiport protein) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased growth and yield -Increased dry biomass -Increased yield -Increased yield -Increased salt tolerance by over-accumulation of Na⁺ in vacuole 	Behera et al., (2022); Balasubramaniam et al., (2023); Birhanu, (2020); Shehata and Ibrahim, (2023)

Conclusion

Salinity stress poses a major challenge to crop production, particularly in arid regions. Understanding the genetic, physiological, and biochemical mechanisms of salt tolerance is essential for developing resilient vegetable crops. Strategies such as conventional breeding, grafting, genetic engineering, and agronomic interventions, including plant growth regulators and microbial inoculants, have shown promise in mitigating salinity effects. Advancements in molecular biology, such as gene editing and marker-assisted selection, can further enhance salt tolerance.

Future efforts should integrate genetic, agronomic, and technological approaches to develop high-yielding, salt-tolerant crops, ensuring sustainable agricultural productivity under saline conditions.

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NS, DT, SS, JV, B, TS conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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